

Effects of Social Responsibility in the Production of Stress

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ABSTRACT

India, the country of uniqueness, knowledge & purity. Literature on family studies in India has grown to a large extent in the last two decades, although such studies are scattered. This paper presents some untold truth on families in India aiming to provide bases for analyzing research, particularly in the area of family development. By observing the furious scenario of socio- familial stress & violence, one can easily realize the need of this paper. Indian families are classified as patrilineal and matrilineal according to the lineage or descent by father or mother. The family structure is conceptualized as the configuration of role, power, and status and relationships in the family which depends upon the families socio-economic background, family pattern, and extent of urbanization. Marriage practices are emphasized covering subjects such as marriage patterns, selection of marriage partner, age at marriage, age at consummation of marriage, marriage rituals, financial exchanges and divorce. In spite of urbanization and industrialization in the contemporary Indian society, the family institution continues to play a central role in the lives of people. There are many social practices, responsible for putting pressure on a person unnecessarily. This stress is a major contributing factor for a series of psychological disturbances, like Depression, Frustration, Suicidal tendency etc; these in turn leads to several physical problems, like Diabetes mellitus, Irritable Bowel Syndrome, several Cardio-vascular disturbances e.t.c.

KEYWORDS: Effects of Social Responsibility, Stress, Man Made Stress, Era of Copying, Era of Competition, Social Psychology

INTRODUCTION

In this so-called Modern civilization, the mankind dedicated their labour for a virtual future. The life-cycle of the modern society is running in an ambiguous manner, completely devoid of principles. This modern era deserves some titles, like 1) the 'era of copying', & 2) the 'era of unhealthy competition'.

If one can able to observe modern scenario of the social lives, he/she can easily encountered the trend of copying, where persons copying each other blindly without any principle. More dangerous is that, they are copying each other's negative characters & qualities. This is one of the major cause of the malfunctioning family, which in turn disturbed the social equilibrium.

Competition & comparison these two terms are dangerously injected within the society because of many reasons. Yes, competitive mentality has two equal sides, i.e. positive & negative. Competition is positive in those cases where, competition is done in a healthy manner, with one's self or in a humanitarian manner; totally devoid of short-cuts & negative mentalities.

These above mentioned characters of the society play a significant role in the production of stress in social animals, i.e. in humans. Stress is very common in living beings and not at all a problem, till it is confined within the manageable limits. When a machine works continuously, stress is an inevitable resultant in that case; as human body is a self-

manageable instrument or machine, stress is also common in this case. But stresses from unnecessary circumstances or from non-idealistic situations are not at all appreciable by any means.

Being the social animal, all have to take several responsibilities both in families & outside of the families (Office, Street, social life e.t.c.); but the nature, extent and character of responsibilities must be guided by a strict principle & protocol. Responsibilities often leads to state of expectation for the family members from each other. These expectations may be one sided or both sided. One- sided expectations may lead to a state of mismatched expectations, which leads to a state of dissatisfaction for both parties and ultimately leads to a state of frustration, anger, depression and helplessness. These can collectively termed as stress in the psychological domain. To match the expectation level, when one have to perform more duties & unwanted stuffs, that can significantly cause stress in physical domain along with the psychological domain. So, broadly one can classify stress into two broad categories- 1) Psychological stress & 2) Physical stress.

FAMILY:

In the context of human society, a **family** (from Latin: *familia*) is a group of people related either by consanguinity (by recognized birth), affinity (by marriage or other relationship), or co-residence (as implied by the etymology of the English word "family"¹) or some combination of these. A family is a group of people who are related to each other, especially grandparents, parents, sons ,daughter ,brother, sister, uncles, aunts, spouses, cousins.

The family in India is often understood as an ideal homogenous unit with strong coping mechanisms. It is a basic, cohesive, and integral unit of the larger social systems. Moreover, families in a large and culturally diverse country such as India have plurality of forms that vary with class, ethnicity, and individual choices. Its members are bound by interpersonal relationships in a wider network of role and social relations. The family is the basic and important unit of society because of the role it plays in generation of human

capital resources and the power that is vested in it to influence individual, household, and community behavior. The family is the first line of defense especially for children and a major factor in their survival, health, education, development, and protection. It is also a major source of nurturance, emotional bonding and socialization, and a link between continuity and change. It has the major potential to provide stability and support when there are problems. Human development can, thus, be enhanced by enriching family life. Families in India are undergoing vast changes like increasing divorce and separation rates, domestic violence, inter-generational conflicts, social problems of drug abuse, juvenile delinquency etc. as the resultant of unwanted stressors. These changes indicate the inability to cope with the pressures of the modern life. Yet, the majority seems to have survived and is able to modify, adjust and adapt to changing social norms, values and structures, and have demonstrated a unique strength in keeping together despite the growing stress and strain.

FAMILY STRUCTURE & COMPOSITION IN INDIA

Family may be broadly defined as a unit of two or more persons united by marriage, blood, adoption, or consensual union, in general consulting a single household, interacting and communicating with each other .

Figure 1. Diagram of the conceptual framework of family structure. From *Conceptual frameworks for understanding family. Enhancing the role of the family as an agency for social and economic development* (Unit for Family Studies Report, pp. 16-41), by Desai, 1994, Bombay, India: TISS.

There was virtually no scope to exit without being a member of a family. According to Census of India, Indian families comprise largely of **nuclear family** structure with **joint families** forming about a fifth of the total households Dr. S. Das & Dr. G. Banerjee classified the families into several types of family structures:

- A. Single member households (a man or woman in one household)
- B. Nuclear pair (only married couple),
- C. Nuclear family (a married couple with or without children)
- D. Collaterally extended (two or more married couples among whom there is a sibling bond, normally brothers plus their unmarried children)
- E. Supplemented collateral joint (a collateral joint family with unmarried, divorced, widowed relatives, typically such supplemented relatives are the widowed mother or widower father or an unmarried sibling)
- F. Lineal extended (two couples between whom there is a lineal link, usually between parents and married son or married daughter)
- G. Supplemented lineal joint (a lineal joint family plus unmarried, divorced or widowed relatives who do not belong to either of the lineally linked nuclear unmarried brother)
- H. Lineal collateral joint (three or more couples linked lineally or collaterally, typically, parents and their married sons plus the unmarried children of the couple)
- I. Supplemented lineal collateral joint (a lineal collateral joint family plus unmarried, widowed, separated relatives who belong to none of the nuclear families lineally and collaterally linked)
- J. Unclassified Category After the consideration this above classification, it is important to take a short snap towards forms of nuclear family, which are-
 - I. **Broken nuclear** — a fragment of a former nuclear family, e.g., a widow with unmarried children living together;
 - II. **Supplemented nuclear** — a nuclear family plus one or more unmarried / separated / widowed relatives of the parents, other than married children).

Family Characteristics:

Most of the demographic characteristics, socio-religious beliefs and practices influence the nature of the Indian family system and also reflect the changes taking place in it. The Indian family is by and large patriarchal in structure. In a patriarchal family set up, all male members, that is, husband, elder brother and father, perform duties like **decision making** for the rest of the family, and their **physical and moral protection**. This patriarchal set up is changing slowly towards equalitarian interaction among the educated, urban middle classes, and also among some rural set ups. Even in matrilineal and matrilocal cultures patriarchy seems to be prevalent in the form of power held by the brother and not by the women herself. **These type of responsibilities can create an atmosphere of respect, expectation & dissatisfaction simultaneously. Not fulfilling of the expectation can create a state of dissatisfaction & anger in both parties, which leads to a state of in cooperation, frustration & depression.**

Patriarchal structure $\frac{3}{4}$ roles, responsibility, control, and distribution of resources within the family are strictly determined by age, gender and generation. The

establishment of the family system is believed to be mainly for the fulfillment of religious obligations like ancestor worship, begetting a male child and passing social religious traditions to the next generation.

One of the few surviving bastions of women power are the Khasis of Meghalaya with a matrilineal system of family. The power, wealth, and rights of inheritance are vested in the women. However, found that with passage of time the matrilineal system has undergone dramatic change due to education, technology and politics. The younger generation is raising the issue to move towards some form of patrilineal system though the elders feel the existing matrilineal form should continue. But along with many good sides, these upliftment & up gradation leaves several dark residues also, like *arrogance, whipping tendency, disrespect towards each other, hyper-individualistic mentality.*

A joint family is a large family where the grandparents, **father**, mother, uncle, aunty and their children live unitedly under one roof. In the joint family system, every member makes financial contribution to the common fund and share common rights in the household property.

In joint family many type of responsibility present and it divided into all family member. Just like finance, decision maker, common right in property

In financial responsibility every family member contribute money but when one or more family member cannot contribute their finance then the stress will arise who contribute more finance .

In other think all family member contribute their finance but cannot fulfill their economy condition then every family member get into stress.

In decision maker who make decision for family but one of the family member cannot support this then stress will arise here.

Interpersonal Relationships: Marital, Parental & Parent- Child Relationships

Husband-wife relationship is the basic and most important amongst the network of relationships on which a family revolves. Healthy relations facilitate the spouses not only to perform their roles effectively but also help in the proper socialization of the children. On the other hand, marital conflict leads to familiar disorganization and has negative consequences on the upbringing of children. Thus, the quality of interaction between a husband and a wife has repercussions on the whole family.

Parent-children conflicts with regards to individual freedom and double standards giving greater freedom to sons than daughters, is a recurring feature and has been noted in many studies. A girl child is allowed to remain a child only for short period of life. It is always stressed that her relationship with her natal home is temporary. Parents tend to discriminate among boys and girls not only in terms of reinforcing speech, activity and play, but also in terms of food, education and other material possessions in India. Many of the social customs and rituals favour or promote child abuse. Indian society makes a relative underestimation of girls and views them as a family liability. Girls get less autonomy and freedom from parents than boys.

Thus, the causes of stress in this section are:

1. FOR MARITAL RELATION-

- Spending of Quality time is minimum
- Distance in husband- wife relationship after the birth of child
- Distance in sexual relations between husband- wife

2. FOR THE CHILD DEVELOPMENT-

- Putting of unnecessary pressure on child to follow social trend
- Injecting the poison of comparison within the child
- Spending of quality time is minimum
- Introducing culture of compensation & punishment
- Dependency on the electronic gadgets
- Too much pampering attitude of the nature
- Not fulfillment of the academic expectation from the child
- Distance between parent & child.
- Unhealthy atmosphere between the parents
- Discriminating behavior of the parents between the children
- Development of competition derived selfishness
- Lack of inter-personal respect between parent & child
- Dominating bossing attitude of the parents e.t.c.

Sibling Relationships

Sibling relationship is recognized as unique among close human relationships because siblings share a common genetic heritage and common early experience within the family. The exchange patterns of emotional support are established among the siblings during early years. Sibling relationship is also marked by discord when paternal authority is weak or absent. Such conflict is an important dimension of sibling relations. Herzberger and Hall state that boys and girls may have different expectations when siblings are involved in the conflict. Severe sibling violence was found to be more prevalent among boys. Furthermore, when younger children were victimized by an older sibling they sought help from parents. Thus, children recognized that aggression against younger siblings is wrong. As joint family system is one of the basic features of Indian society, it becomes essential to consider the cordial and conflicting relationship between secondary relatives.

So, causes of stress in this section are:

- Discriminating attitude of the parents
- Comparative nature between the siblings
- Mentality mismatch
- Difference in ideologies & choices
- Unfriendly environment between the siblings
- Hyper-individualistic mentality e.t.c.

Mother-in-Law and Daughter-in-Law Relationships

The mother-in-law occupies a dominant position and plays an important role in the social life of the daughter-in-law. This is one area where very few studies have been done. The elder woman finds the younger was disrupting unity among brothers; the younger finds the elder to be intolerably demanding and dominating. The relationship of women with sisters-in-law is another area which has dearth of studies although it is of great significance in a joint household.

So, the causes of stress in this section are:

1. FOR DAUGHTER- IN LAW-

- Difficulty in the adaptation of new family environment
- Dominating behavior of the in-laws
- Mentality miss match

- Lack of care from in-laws
- Lack of care from the husband
- One-sided behavior of he husband
- Marital violence e.t.c.

2. FOR MOTHER-IN-LAW:-

- So-called generation gap
- Mentality miss match
- One sided behavior from son
- Loneliness e.t.c.

Conclusion:

Family has been recognized as a basic unit of society and is a link between individual and community. The structure of the family continues to be patriarchal. A number of changes have been observed in the patterns of marriage such as age at marriage, inter-caste marriage, etc. A relative increase is noticed in divorce cases in urban areas. It was quite common in the past but at that time families were more stable and provided adequate security in terms of physical, social and emotional needs. Current trends indicate that there is a definite change in the basic system of family, especially the role of elders and disharmony in husband-wife relationship. Divorce rates are testimony to the increasing fragility of husband-wife relationship. Migration has major implications on women and children.

To cope up with the common stressors of everyday life & to avoid unwanted stressors which can results into stress, one have to be wise & rational. Worthless expectations making and competitive mentality are two basic pillars of this stressed society. So, to lead a healthy life, it is important to focus on the definitive goals, but in a holistic manner.

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